

SEO STRATEGIES DEVELOPMENT FOR DEVELOPMENT PROJECTS EFFECTIVE PROMOTION**Fomicheva E.***master's degree, State University of Management***Abstract**

The article analyzes the development of SEO (search engine optimization) strategies for promoting real estate development projects. It examines the behavior of the target audience and the specifics of search queries in the real estate sector. The impact of local SEO optimization and multimedia content on increasing the visibility of developers' websites is studied. The importance of a comprehensive approach is emphasized, including technical site optimization and external factors such as backlinks. Key factors of a successful SEO strategy are considered, including adaptation to the long development cycles of real estate projects. The research findings may be useful for real estate development companies and digital marketing specialists.

Keywords: search engine optimization (SEO), real estate development projects, digital marketing, real estate, search queries, optimization.

Introduction

In the highly competitive real estate market, effective promotion of development projects has become a key factor for success. Traditional marketing techniques, such as media advertising and outdoor advertising, are gradually giving way to digital tools. Digital marketing heavily relies on email marketing, affiliate marketing, and search engine optimization (SEO). These methods can significantly impact business outcomes, including revenue, website traffic, and consumer engagement [1]. In an era when over 90% of users begin their property search online, a well-crafted SEO strategy allows development companies to significantly increase the visibility of their projects in search engines, leading to traffic growth and higher conversion rates.

The aim of this study is to develop a comprehensive SEO strategy for promoting real estate development projects, taking into account the specifics of the real estate market. The research objectives include examining key factors affecting the success of SEO in this sector, analyzing target audience behavior and competitive landscapes, and identifying effective optimization methods tailored to developers' needs.

The scientific novelty of the work lies in a comprehensive approach to SEO strategy development, integrating both traditional and innovative promotion methods. In particular, aspects such as local optimization, the use of multimedia content, and the development of strategies for complex queries are explored. The findings may be useful for both real estate development companies and digital marketing professionals.

Main part. Theoretical foundations of SEO and its adaptation for development projects

The practice of SEO encompasses a set of techniques aimed at increasing a website's visibility in search engine results. Elements of SEO include keyword optimization, on-page and off-page optimization, enhancing user experience, and technical aspects such as website loading speed and mobile responsiveness. While these aspects are important across industries, development projects have unique features that require a specialized approach.

When applied to development projects, SEO must **take into account the extended cycles** of real estate development. This means that the strategy should be

long-term, as developers often face the need to promote properties that are still under construction. Content plays a crucial role here, including the creation of long-form articles about the advantages of future properties, video overviews, and virtual tours, which help generate user interest long before the properties are completed.

In real estate development, the geographical aspect is vital. Most user queries are linked to specific districts or cities, making **local optimization** critically important. This involves using regional keywords such as «buy an apartment in New York» or «new developments in California» and creating pages for each real estate project with detailed information about its location, infrastructure, and transport accessibility.

Understanding target audience behavior is a key aspect of a successful SEO strategy. Freely available information on user search queries can provide deep insights that enrich commonly accepted market demand and supply statistics. This information can also be used as a sole determinant for predicting changes in housing prices with a time lag sufficient for making decisions about buying or selling a particular property or controlling the real estate market [2]. These queries are generally broad in nature, requiring developers to provide educational content on their websites, helping attract potential clients in the early stages of their decision-making process. Analytics can increase customer satisfaction and operational efficiency [3].

Commercial queries such as «buy an apartment» or «apartments in new buildings» appear at later stages of the user journey when they are ready to consider specific properties for purchase. For developers, it is essential to optimize property listing pages for these queries. Targeted SEO techniques can be employed, including optimizing titles, meta descriptions, and page content that contains relevant information about prices, floor plans, and purchase conditions.

It is also worth noting that a significant number of users are interested in different types of real estate (residential, commercial) and make queries focused on long-term investments, such as «real estate investments» or «buy an apartment for rent». This highlights the importance of adapting content and SEO strategies for different target audience segments. Artificial intelligence (AI) tools can be used for this purpose, offering unlimited possibilities for data collection and finding

the most suitable content for different types of clients [4].

Key factors for a successful SEO strategy for development projects

A successful SEO strategy for developers must consider several key factors. The **creation of high-quality and relevant content** that meets both informational and commercial user queries is essential. For example, providing detailed property descriptions, high-quality images, video overviews, and 3D tours can significantly increase the time users spend on the website and improve conversion rates.

Technical optimization of the website is crucial. Page loading speed, mobile responsiveness, and user-friendly navigation play important roles for both users and search engines. According to recent data from Google, more than 50% of users leave a site if it takes longer than three seconds to load, emphasizing the need to address technical aspects.

Another important aspect is **building backlinks**. For developers, it is important to increase the number of quality backlinks by securing links from authoritative sources. These could be publications in industry-specific media, thematic blogs, or partner resources related to real estate. It has been proven that high-quality backlinks improve a website's search rankings and increase trust from search engines [5].

Analyzing competitors' websites is a crucial step in developing an effective SEO strategy. This allows developers to identify competitors' strengths and weaknesses and uncover untapped niches for promotion. In the development sector, competitors often employ aggressive SEO tactics, including link-building, content marketing, and paid promotion tools.

For example, competitor analysis can reveal the most effective key queries driving their traffic, as well as their content marketing strategies. It is also important to study their approaches to local SEO optimization, which allows real estate companies to better tailor their strategies to specific markets.

Developing a comprehensive SEO strategy for development projects

The development of an SEO strategy for real estate projects should involve several stages. The first stage involves **market and competitor analysis** to identify key queries and determine the target audience segments. The second stage focuses on **content strategy**, including creating pages for each property, publishing helpful content for different types of queries, and producing multimedia materials.

Next, the website undergoes **technical optimization**, which includes improving loading speed, ensuring mobile compatibility, and setting up user-friendly navigation. **Regular analysis** is a vital component, enabling developers to adjust their strategy based on changes in user search behavior and search engine algorithms. Web analytics tools and SEO performance monitoring are used for this purpose. AI and machine learning (ML) play a significant role in improving this aspect [6].

The final stage involves **working with external factors**, such as building backlinks and engaging with industry-specific resources. A comprehensive approach that integrates all these elements enables real estate companies to effectively promote their projects and achieve high search engine rankings. The analysis of key aspects of developing SEO strategies for real estate projects is presented in table 1.

Table 1.

SEO strategy elements and their impact on the development projects promotion [5, 7-10]

SEO element	Description	Impact on promotion	Statistics
Technical optimization	Optimization of website loading speed, mobile responsiveness, meta tags.	Speeds up indexing, improves user experience.	Loading time < 3 seconds increases conversion by 30%.
Content strategy	Creating unique and valuable content (articles, blogs, real estate descriptions).	Attracts organic traffic, retains users.	Over 70% of homebuyers search for information online before purchasing.
Local SEO optimization	Using keywords related to the location of real estate (neighborhoods, cities).	Attracts local traffic, increases conversion chances.	Local SEO increases the likelihood of inquiries by 50% for developers.
Backlinks	Acquiring links from authoritative websites, engaging with external platforms and media.	Enhances search engine trust, improves ranking.	56% of SEO specialists consider links a key factor in ranking improvement.
Mobile optimization	Adapting the website's interface and functionality for mobile platforms (smartphones, tablets).	Increases user engagement, reduces bounce rate.	As of early 2024, 59,4% of traffic comes from mobile devices
Analytics and monitoring	Tools for tracking traffic, user behavior, and website rankings.	Allows real-time strategy adjustments.	Websites with regular analytics grow traffic 20% faster.

The presented data highlights the necessity of an integrated approach to SEO optimization for the successful promotion of development projects. Technical optimization, including site loading speed and responsiveness, improves user experience and speeds up in-

dexing, leading to increased conversion rates. A content strategy focused on creating unique and valuable content attracts organic traffic, reflecting the growing interest of users in online information before purchasing real estate. Local SEO optimization using geographically relevant keywords increases the likelihood

of inquiries from local users, while backlinks from authoritative sources build search engine trust and improve website rankings. Mobile adaptation is becoming critically important as a significant portion of users search for real estate via mobile devices.

The chart (fig. 1) shows the steady rise in mobile traffic globally from 2012 to 2024 (1,56% vs. 59,41%) [10].

Figure 1. Mobile traffic growth 2012-2024

This trend underscores the importance of optimizing websites for mobile devices as part of SEO strategies. Regular analysis and monitoring allow for timely adjustments in promotion strategies, accelerating traffic growth. Therefore, the successful promotion of development projects requires the integration of all the mentioned SEO elements into a unified strategy.

Conclusion

The study identified key aspects of developing effective SEO strategies for promoting development projects. Given the long-term cycles of real estate projects, a comprehensive approach is required, including regular content updates, adaptation to audience needs, and sustained interest throughout the construction stages. Informational queries dominate the early stages of property search, emphasizing the importance of educational content. At the decision-making stage, commercial queries increase, necessitating the optimization of property pages and a particular focus on local SEO and mobile adaptation. Technical SEO aspects, such as page load speed and site responsiveness, are critical for user retention. External factors, including quality backlinks, remain essential for improving site rankings. Therefore, effective SEO strategies in development must account for long project timelines, high competition, and diverse queries. Future research may focus on multimedia content and methods for analyzing the competitive landscape.

References

1. Rizun N., Baj-Rogowska A. Can web search queries predict prices change on the real estate market? // IEEE Access. – 2021. – V. 9. – P. 70095-70117.
2. Bykovskii, G., Dutot, V. Machine learning and artificial intelligence in real estate marketing: a systematic review // International Research Meeting in Business and Management. – 2022. – Nice, France.

URL: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/365781052_Machine_learning_and_artificial_intelligence_in_a_real_estate_marketing_a_systematic_review (date of application: 06.10.2024).

3. Rana A., Kaithwas A. The shifting landscape of digital marketing: trends and predictions for the future // Phalanx: A Quarterly Review for Continuing Debate. – 2023. – V. 18. – I. 2. – P. 35-42.

4. Dave M. The role of backlinks in search engine ranking // International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer Science and Software Engineering. – 2013. – V. 3(4). – P. 596-599.

5. Pshychenko D. Evaluation of the effectiveness of implementing AI-based CRM systems // Innovacionnaja nauka. – 2024. – V. 7-2/2024. – P. 40-45.

6. Kuznetsov I.A., Bobunov A.Yu., Bushuev S.A., Smirnov A.P., Pshichenko D.V. Integration of Big Data into recommendation systems: content personalization technologies // Competitiveness in the Global World: Economics, Science, Technology. – 2024. – V. 9. – P. 56-61.

7. Google shares new mobile page speed guidelines / Collective Measures // URL: <https://www.collectivemeasures.com/insights/google-mobile-page-speed-guidelines> (date of application: 11.10.2024).

8. Real estate in a digital age / National Association of Realtors USA // URL: <https://www.nar.realtor/research-and-statistics/research-reports/real-estate-in-a-digital-age> (date of application: 12.10.2024).

9. Ahmad U. F., Mahdee J., Abu Bakar N. Search engine optimisation (SEO) strategy as determinants to enhance the online brand positioning // F1000Research. – 2024. – V. 11. – P. 714.

10. Desktop vs Mobile Market Share Worldwide // StatCounter Global Stats. URL: <https://gs.statcounter.com/platform-market-share/desktop-mobile/worldwide/#monthly-201001-202401> (date of application: 13.10.2024).